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Seeking Common Ground: Journeys Landscape and Inner Realms

Jeremy P. H. Morgan

It was from discussions with my father who was a Geographer (human-political) that I became aware of the term “Feng Shui (風水)” when we were walking in Welsh hill country looking at the landscape around us and my father explained to me the concepts that underlay Geomancy in Ancient Chinese Taoist cosmology. I became aware that certain Chinese concepts were bound to the principles of divination. Understanding the world in both physical and psychic terms of materiality and spirituality was fascinating. During these walks, I became aware that the spaces of Nature were also “landscapes” that were created from processes of geology and were overlaid by the motion of weather as functions of both time and space and by extension the Eternal and Infinite. Was motion that was the underlying and unifying reality? The landscape was a profound experience and concept.

It was a pivotal moment in my life. Within a few years, I would be at art school and thus began a journey that would infuse my art practice, which is ongoing. As my art education developed, I became interested in three particular areas of cultural activity. The first was the British and European Romantic landscape tradition and its development and implications founded in the concepts of the sublime. Secondly, it was the Chinese Shan Shui tradition and other aspects of Chinese painting. After that, the experience of both European and American abstract painting gave me much to reflect upon. I began to consider the possible relationship between the seemingly distant traditions of Chinese landscape painting and British/European landscape painting and particular aspects of Abstraction.

When I first saw images of Chinese landscape paint-

Figure 1. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *One Moment Still*. Acrylic on muslin, 36"×72", 2018.

ings and compared them to Western landscape traditions, I sensed a distinct difference in the fundamental approach beyond the most apparent material differences. The first was the material nature of ink painting on silk and or paper! In the Western watercolor traditions, especially the work of J. M. W. Turner and Alexander Cozens, I sensed the possibility of connection. The similarities became very intriguing when I became acquainted with the improvisational methods of some ink painting traditions and compared them with Cozens's experiments! Alexander Cozens created a "Blot" technique that allowed a spontaneous process in the studio to create essential abstractions through mark-making to suggest landscape-based imagery. There was a solid connection to the Chinese splash ink approach "Shui Mo Hua (水墨畫)" which encouraged the mind and material process to generate imagery that evoked rather than depicted scenery.

In the processes of watercolor, it is both the subtleties and sensitivity in the fluidity of watercolor and the role of the white space/surface of the paper as a receptacle of mark-making that is distinct as opposed to the weight and materiality of oil paint. On reflection, I

sensed an aesthetic resonance between East and West.

It was clear to me that the Chinese artist painted from the body into space compared to the Western art tradition (until the advent of the landscape tradition) that the artist painted toward the body. This realization coincided with another thought as I considered the ideas of how in a furthermore more significant factors of separation based on the metaphysical & spiritual traditions of both cultures. The Abrahamic traditions (Judaic-Christian, Muslim) had a theocratic architect who created the world, whilst China recognized the universe was born of an impersonal cosmic ordering. In one conception (the Western) the world was made on the other hand the vision of Chinese consciousness was that there was a seamless fusion between the world at its inception and within its fluorescence where past present and future were synchronous. Nature was neither a construct nor a notion but the origin and context of our being.

At the close of my undergraduate study, I had begun synthesizing those historic manifestations and exploring the concept of Abstraction. In part, abstraction evolved from the evolution of landscape painting and

Figure 2. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Almost Gone*. Acrylic on canvas with silk, 72"×56", 2018.

Figure 3. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Origins*. Acrylic on canvas, 20"×16", 2019.

Figure 4. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Fracture*. Acrylic and photocollage on canvas, 12"×12", 2020.

Figure 5. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Deep Time*. Acrylic on canvas, 72"×72", 2020.

the spatiality of imagery based on landscape. The transformation of landscape space and its growing significance within the Western Canon began to evolve through work such as Cézanne and Monet into proto-Abstraction. In addition, it was the precise relationship between the metaphysical and spiritual context of image making in relationship to landscape in both the Western European romantic traditions and within Chinese painting, particularly Shan Shui. The very language of art discussion, particularly in Chinese and Japanese, is an erudition regarding the function of art as a form of spiritual manifestation, not in the sense that it illustrated stories but rather that consciousness of a spiritual nature was manifest within the creative process. This was a key to my development as a painter and allowed me to gain the confidence to think about the possibilities of art as a form of spiritual practice.

Within the tradition of Asian aesthetics is the synthesis of consciousness and action where the West tends to objectify the world into object/subject relations. I found that aspects of Eastern awareness were bound more conceptions of a flowing continuum.

The dynamic possibilities of energy both of one's own body and its complexities of electrical and chemical dynamics began to illicit a sense of direction as that body and consciousness interacted with the phenomenal world. A long practice of martial arts (Judo, Shotokan Karate, Taekwondo, and Tai Chi) helped in my comprehension of

the role of Choreography (also Calligraphic) in relating to context (time-space) and environment.

As a painter, I focused on exploring the topic of Landscape as both topographic/phenomenal and as spiritualized space, philosophical & cosmic. Equally, I am intrigued by aspects of Abstraction about processes of visual creation in which the abstract is arguably more "real" than Mimesis (optical fidelity and representation). My talks with my father allowed me to consider how nature can reveal and expand our understanding of our being and that of nature and human nature and our appreciation of both structure and time in unique ways. The phenomenal world what the eye and body experience form one level of reality the mechanisms of understanding the world come through our senses then there is consciousness which assists in other levels of understanding. As I considered the landscape as a motif in pictorial terms I also began to realize that I see with my eyes open and equally I see when they are closed the notion of what is out there as opposed to bodies within become uncertain in ways that I found most interesting. Painting in relation to the natural world meant reflecting on what I had seen and what I had sensed doing. I found a route to the abstract which had begun with my paintings based on the human body in motion relating to my experiences with the martial arts.

The figural works that became more abstract than I had done in art school and the landscape "Pleine Aire"

Figure 6. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Akasha*. Acrylic on canvas, 72"×56", 2021.

Figure 7. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Within and Beyond*. Acrylic on canvas, 72"×48", 2021.

painting I did in Wales seemed somehow connected. It was my tutor who suggested that what I have been doing in both instances is bound to my interest in the sensation of movement and that what he thought I should think about doing was not to paint things that are moving (such as clouds the body etc.) but rather to paint as if myself were moving and give an account of that experience. That was the key that would allow me to push further into the realms of the abstract, which seems to be more accurate than what Mimesis has suggested.

Our ocular structure binds our vision field in our natural state and the space of nature. We see the world bound by a circle! As human habitation developed beyond the rudimentary structure of shelters and as humans began to construct architectural forms so too did the paradox of the frame! Windows and doors were “portals” through which we were now formatting visual experience and thus began a new relation to “imagery”. A new sense of pictorialism emerged. The Image is bound to visibility as an echo is to the originating sound it is in essence a removal presence function to announce

absence.

Chinese painting navigates the correlation between what is visible and what may exist within consciousness and corresponds to states of awareness as much as identifiability. These are worlds of seeming or apparitions, evocations that are not documents of reportage but sensation and the iteration of psychic fidelity rather than the optical facts.

Watching one occasion a graduate student at the China Academy of Art began the process of painting from a 17th-century masterwork I watched her prepare. First the grinding of the ink, then the selection of the brushes. I then watched as she carefully placed the brush in part into the inkstone well and towards the paper. Then as the brush touched the paper and as the ink met the paper I realized I was witness to something quite phenomenal: this Artist using her materials was creating energies in space rather than marks upon the surface! The paper functioned as a spatial receptacle. This was critically significant as it allowed me to reconsider my approach to the notion of surface.

Artists such as Turner were groundbreaking in their dramatic break from pictorial approaches. The Western perspectival structure is predicated upon the idea that the surface of the painting is the foundation of two pyramids: one projecting outwards (the viewers' space), the other inwards (the realm of the picture). In essence, the structure is spectatorial: outer viewers and inner images. By contrast, Chinese perspectives offer a more invitational aspect with relative positions of height and depth (negating orthogonal linear vectors) determined by degrees of magnitude and density of marks and tones. Turner anticipates the aspect of the openness of Chinese landscapes with his use of both atmospheric density changes and the concomitant dissolving of many solid forms into aqueous and Gaseous ambience.

There is another Western artist before the Twentieth Century who began to address a more Eastern sensibility. Claude Monet is among the first painters in the West to reconsider the phenomenon of light, sensation, diffusion, and dematerialization of the optical world. These two, Turner and Monet dissolved the objective reality of forms in space of forms disposed in space and time into Ambient Chromatic and tonal fields. They painted the dynamic energies of the phenomenal world... A world that is perhaps indivisible?

As a painter, I am deeply interested in my materials. The brush and touch relate to the playing of musical instruments. Painting may function as a wordless encounter within "the space of time" or "the time of space". It can establish its manifest consciousness as it archives the psyche. Painting is as much bound to time as it is indicative of spatiality. Painting is the confluence process of space, time, and energy to reality within time and bound implicitly to space. It is a process unique in its ability to fuse psyche immateriality within a timeframe. The utter creation of a painting is an act of duration that enfolds multiple dimensions of time; thus, that "time frame" is multi-time-dimensional. Painting is a form of chronicle as much as it is an indication of space. It exists as ever present containing time while the photograph is an extraction from the time continuum. While graduating from the Royal Academy Schools in London, I began to use acrylic paint. This material allows me to explore the notions of fluidity more fully than thickness. At the same time, I began to reconsider the role of substrate and surface and to reconsider "where the surface of the work was". What I saw in Chinese art was the seamless connection between where the brush was in the hand of the artist and the space into which they painted, and I began to consider that possibility for myself. As a Western artist who wanted to consider that approach and yet respect the uniqueness of Chinese traditions, I wanted

to adopt some of what I sensed was the ability of Chinese artists to move seamless from here to there! I began to use unprimed canvas (later muslin and silk) and mediums to create "invisible drawing" later adding inks and diluted acrylic allowing for spontaneity as a critical element in the creative process allowing an unconscious aspect to the process. This then became a new way to approach my painting where in my relationship through the material of my paint with the materiality of the surfaces I was using canvas later silk and muslin. There was then of sense of fusion between myself and the intimations of a physical space through

Figure 8. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Atramental Luminosity*. Acrylic on digital print on silk, over canvas with acrylic, 72"×36", 2021.

Figure 9. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Occurrence*. Acrylic on canvas, 24"×18", 2021.

Figure 10. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Surface Infinities*. Acrylic and mediums on canvas, 10"×10", 2021.

the agency of the surface of the work.

In the mid-1990s, I had the opportunity to visit China. It was a significant moment in my journey and evolution as an artist. I first visited Hangzhou after a brief stop in Shanghai. At what is now known as the China Academy of Art (then the Zhejiang Academy of Art). On that occasion, I was leading a group of students from the San Francisco Art Institute, continuing a relatively new tradition of international traveling created by the then Dean of SFAI Fred Martin (and Ming Ren a Graduate of the CAA and later SFAI) from that moment I was to begin to understand a little more about the culture that I had learned about remotely by reading and artworks.

In the classes on both Calligraphy and landscape, what became immediately apparent was the true foundational significance of Calligraphy as the most significant factor in generating visual pictorial imagery.

In time, also can the realization of unique attributes of the Chinese perspective, as opposed to the Western perspective is how they function within pictorial traditions, and how they had a concomitant and significant importance as a means of engaging the viewer! By contrast, the Western static recessional structure has a very different function beyond organizing spatial relations. Implicit within what is the perspective

of structures is the notion of the picture plane as the effective base of 2 pyramids! The apex of one is the vanishing point within the image itself the other is located in the eyes of the viewer. Thus, the viewer is carefully separated optically from the space that they view as it recedes away from the picture plane, which is the physical surface of the painting into the apparent depth, the point being that such images are bound to the notion of looking through the window at what lays beyond that window.

In the Chinese system, it is a recognition of depth perception and levels of recession and magnitude of elements within the painting. Beyond, the Chinese image expects and encourages interaction by moving into and through the picture through visual pathways that invite intimacy, as they also suggest magnitude and vastness!

Equally arguably to is the notion that in the Chinese painting, when is the perception of the world as forms of energy and elements not so much the objects of structure, but rather structure itself is formed by energy, every mountain or cloud depicted within those energies created as a manifestation. There is a synthesis here between intent and realization.

In the work of painters, particularly in the Northern Sung (960-1127) dynasty and then the Southern Sung (1127-1279) could see the deep consideration of the role

Figure 11. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Presence*. Acrylic on polyester, 70"×54", 2022.

of vertical orientation and then that of the horizontal in the engagement of both time and space and this as a reflection of the topography of the landscape. But as important was how scroll painting was directly related to time and duration. Looking at a scroll was more like reading in time through space. This was a vital aspect of Chinese (and Japanese) Art in that it gave a time dimension to space. This was in relationship to the duration of how time can be perceived as unfolding and being of measure. In the West, we had the format of the panorama which had more to do with the movement of the neck as it scanned an area in front of the body whereas I believe the Chinese scroll painting has that aspect secondary to the primary one of the experience of time in space and the relationship between time and the eternal and space and the infinite.

What seemed apparent to me within these sophisticated and deeply considered explorations was an understanding of how the human psyche and the natural world were at one as consciousness and that painting literally became a manifestation of that consciousness and its fusion with nature. The artists in China were at one with the universe which they endeavored to relate the experience of through image making.

The work of Ma Yuan, Shi Tao, Fan Kuan, and many others helped me to realize the deep significance of the way within which art was a powerful means by which the psyche could become both manifestation and archive. Also, art could evoke and exemplify the reality of Taoist consciousness.

It seemed to me that the development of abstraction in the West was bound to two distinct aspects: one was of visual development and evolution and equally to the notion and role of language.

My understanding of Chinese Visual-cultural

evolution is that there was a natural fusion between visual and written form. In the West, there developed two distinct paths: one was Image development and the other linguistic. Essentially however in China, there was not that distinction because calligraphy formed the natural connection between what was expressed in either linguistic form or as visual manifestation! The Chinese language evolved in written form from oracular ritual and pictographic forms wherein in its primacy language was as much pictorial as it was as symbolic-linguistic transmission. In the event of such a natural fusion, the distinctions between abstraction and representation are arguably more blurred. As I perceived (without specific knowledge but through observation) was that certain traditions within Chinese art were an affirmation of a cosmic consciousness rooted within Taoist awareness of the experienced fluidity of reality.

It appeared that much of Asian aesthetics was bound to a “non-object” thinking. In place of object structures was a sense of a flowing continuum of shifting interconnected states of being which reflected the intersection of time to the eternal and of space to the infinite.

In many ways, the evolution of abstraction in the West developed as a parallel to expanding consciousness (philosophical, spiritual, and scientific investigations) that gave an expanded sense of understanding the complexities of the world in which we lived. These were bound to move beyond points of what was topographically available to us as the “apparent/perceived visual world”. That which had fixed upon a depiction of the outer world as opposed to the inner structure of it. Perhaps landscape artists were among the first to realize the possibilities of finding something more of essence rather than what had been the dominant trend

Figure 12. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Embraced by Distances*. Acrylic on silk over canvas, 24"×66", 2023.

Figure 13. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *In the Realm of Silence*. Acrylic on canvas, 30"×24", 2023.

towards Mimesis in Western pictorial development. Beyond issues of the seeming dematerializing of the world, many artists sought to find ways to express that which lay beyond immediately visible. I felt as I began to discover these aspects in Western painting that there were at times correspondences to what I was seeing in Chinese art in the differing visions it was arguably a spiritual and/or philosophical underpinning that led towards finding how it might become possible express or articulate visions oozes of the world beyond its surface structures?

When I saw reproductions of the work of Chang Dai-chien, I found a sense of fusion between Eastern and Western sensibilities that was unique in that it seemed as if two methodologies were in unison. The distinction between Chinese brush and the more amorphous works of Abstract expressionists (Helen Frankenthaler stain and poured paintings was striking!) I realized too that Rinzai Zen had generally influenced the American Abstract Expressionists and that Chinese art traditions were seemingly less appreciated. In Japanese calligraphy was a particular dynamic velocity based on a spontaneous moment, it was also transversal and planer? The work of Chang Dai-chien was very important as it was an exploration of cultural diversity and convergence at the same time! I began to realize the implication of

the cultural possibility of further iterations.

Upon leaving Europe and then living in America, studying and teaching there, and eventually visiting China regularly, I felt the degree of liberation that gave me a means to realize and understand what was of fundamental interest to me.

My first remembered Art was that of J. M. W. Turner the English landscape artist that my father showed me first in books and then in galleries those images of the English landscape and then of the European and beyond started to ignite my imagination. In Turner's work, I sensed how art could contain and articulate the complexities of seeing and announcing visions of art concepts. Turner's immense breadth of technical experimentation and virtuosity were in the service of his poetic sensibility. From the almost at times reductive but evocative mark making to the most lush of oil paint usage he at times seemed to be looking through the world, not at it! The role of transparency was a signature of his awareness of the pellucid world of light and color. His reverence for the natural environment and its processes were the abode of his imagination. His understanding of weather and the movement of air and moisture across topographies was profound. He was a poet of light and space.

Then, in the USA, I began to understand better aspects of the abstract expressionist movement and all of the subtle but definite distinctions between that collective group. I also realized the profundity of both Cubism and Surrealism as both intellectual and experiential in the liberation of Western painting from the constraints of Mimesis.

Abstract Expressionist artists were made up of emigrants partly from Europe and central-Southern America and American-born painters represented a pivotal moment in the evolution of Western painting and also represented the idea of art that would indicate the nature of the consciousness and sentience beyond the optical alone wherein concepts born pm of an inner reflection not to escape the reality but find other ways that reality might be able to be expressed.

My earlier experience of Martial arts training has introduced me to the philosophy of China and Japan. The awareness that I gained from these experiences was formative. In the mid-90s, I started to visit China fairly regularly and visit its various landscapes and then reconsider aspects of the art I had seen from that culture that seemed to be a unique synchronicity of thought and action. There was a perception of what appeared as familiar to me even though I did not have the luxury of a shared language I felt an affinity with the visual traditions that I encountered in China and had previously

Figure 14. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Mirage Aperture*. Acrylic on silk over canvas, 36"×28", 2023.

Figure 15. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Infinite and Beyond*. Acrylic on canvas, 18"×72", 2023.

Figure 16. Jeremy P. H. Morgan. *Phantasmagoria*. Acrylic on canvas, 42"×42", 2023.

observed from a distance.

Artistic practice allows individuals to encounter and navigate the possibilities offered by aspects of freedom. Studio practice for many is related to the process of ritual. The studio becomes a place of contemplation and manifestation. The art of the ancient world was perhaps the result of sacred practice. Within the plurality of a contemporary matrix exists the volition of artists and as they add to the contemporary moment, they exist within the abiding eternal. The aesthetic creative impulse connects through the history of humanity. Consciousness is archived in the moments of artistic realization. I perceive painting to function as a silent witness to both the visible and the invisible. Other forms of art do so but painting is unique in how it holds time(s). How it is a chronicle of time(s) and the vessel of mechanical, chemical, and psychic energy.

I work now with the desire to find a meeting point between what is my British European heritage and my instinctive and intuitive connection to what I perceive within the culture of China and other Asian countries and to find a way through painting to fuse sensibilities that I believe have a common ground which also are often articulated so very differently. I want to respect that distinction but I also want to add to the possibility that there might be ways within which my paintings might allow the traditions of philosophical romanticism and Taoist sensibilities to redefine common ground. My journey evolves now and with my movement going

west to the USA has been of course a journey towards the East. America has been a dynamic and significant connection with its extraordinary landscapes, powerful histories diversity of races and cultures in many ways it is poised between what historically “was” (Europe) to what will be (Asia) thus the cycle continues! The fusion becomes a new reality that in fact is timeless... wherein time touches the eternal and space exists within the infinite.

JEREMY P. H. MORGAN, American based British artist, studied at the Ruskin School of Drawing and Fine Arts at Oxford University between 1974 and 1977. During that period, he was able to study Chinese and Japanese art and became deeply affected by the art of the Song Dynasty and the Chinese Shan-shui tradition. He went to the Royal Academy for graduate study from 1979 to 1982 and was introduced to the American Abstract Expressionism. In 1983-85, he received the Harkness Fellowship and went on to study for his MFA in Painting at the San Francisco Art Institute (Honors 1985). He was an Associate Professor of Painting at the San Francisco Art Institute (33 years, retired in 2022). He has visited China multiple times since 1994, and his engagement with the country and its artists has been a continuing source of meaning and significance to his practice as an artist. His intention is to seek further the means to forge new relations between different cultures.

Editor: Liu Kexin